

PROFILE ON THE ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT OF NURSES DURING COVID-19 PANDEMIC

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 22

Issue 5

Pages: 530-542

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2077

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.12789889

Manuscript Accepted: 06-10-2024

Profile on the Organizational Commitment of Nurses During COVID-19 Pandemic

Michael John A. Castillo*

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

The commitment of an organization shows a worker's psychological connection, loyalty, and devotion to their employer. It is the degree to which staff members identify with the organization's objectives, values, and mission and are willing to work diligently for its success. This quantitative research utilized the descriptive, correlational design in assessing the relationship between profile and organizational commitment among nurses in healthcare institutions in the Province of Cotabato. The findings of the study revealed that the majority of the respondents were young adults or belonging to 19 to 35 years old and the majority of them were females and college degree holders. Furthermore, most of the respondents have served their organization for 3 to 6 years already and the majority of the respondents are connected to a private hospital. Continuance commitment was rated as neither low nor high while affective commitment and normative commitment were rated as high. Overall, the organizational commitment of the respondents was high. Age, sex, educational attainment, years of service, and type of hospital did not have a significant relationship with continuance commitment. Age, sex, educational attainment, years of service, and type of hospital did not have a significant relationship with affective commitment. There was a significant relationship between years of experience and normative commitment while age, sex, educational attainment, and the type of hospital showed no significant relationship with normative commitment. Significant relationships were seen between years of experience and overall organizational commitment as well as type of hospital and overall organizational commitment. Meanwhile age, sex, and educational attainment did not have a significant relationship with overall organizational commitment. In conclusion, years of experience and the type of hospital influence organizational commitment. Longer years of experience translate to higher organizational commitment. Private hospitals have been seen to have increased organizational commitment. As an output of the study, an organizational commitment enhancement plan was created.

Keywords: *descriptive, correlational design, nurses, organizational commitment*

Introduction

"Unless commitment is made, there are only promises and hopes; but no plans"- Ralph Waldo Emerson. The dedication of a professional extends beyond a commitment to a specific organization to include an individual's perspective on their profession and the drive that they have to maintain their interest in their job with an eagerness to strive and adhere to the profession's values and goals.

The Department of Health cited that in December 2021, the number of nurses in the Philippines has been slowly decreasing primarily due to socioeconomic factors. In their latest data, there are only 172,589 registered nurses in the country working in the public and private sectors, representing 19% of the total registered nurses. As 320,352 or 35% of the country's registered nurses are working as migrant healthcare professionals, 292,893 or 32% are either unemployed or non-practitioners, and 137,294, or 14% are working in other professions (DOH, 2021). These data reflect the country's increasingly problematic healthcare employment conditions, which rose from pay discrepancies or inequitable salaries that have been relatively prevalent over the past few years. The unfavorable employment opportunities within the country have led many nurses and other healthcare professionals to waver in their commitment to serve (Valmonte, 2022). This chronic problem in the Philippine Healthcare System has been accentuated by the COVID-19 Pandemic which challenged the efficiency and responsiveness of the provision and delivery of healthcare services (Buchan & Catton, 2021).

The highly contagious and fast-evolving nature of the SARS-CoV-2 has rendered the precautionary measures seemingly ineffective thereby greatly impacting service delivery and human resources for health (Liu, 2020). At the onset of the pandemic, nurses in the Philippines have been struggling to cope with the new demands of addressing healthcare needs as more and more nurses were contracting COVID-19 or were resigning from their jobs en masse amidst the precarious understaffing situations in hospitals even before the pandemic (WHO, 2013). The remaining nurses were left to work for longer hours while enduring low compensation or under short-term contracts which led to exhaustion and low motivation further damaging organizational commitment (Jackson, 2021). In 2021, around 40% of nurses working in private hospitals resigned since the pandemic started (Mendoza, 2021). In concurrence, the Private Hospitals Association of the Philippines in 2021 reported that the severe need for nurses in hospitals to adequately provide healthcare services is crucial to keep the health system afloat (PHAP, 2021).

This necessitated the much-needed shift in the paradigm of the medical profession that is geared toward managing the stress of additional workload and addressing overwhelming challenges brought upon by the illness (American Journal of Nursing, 2021). However, the national government responded in a manner that sought immediate but reactionary solutions that were perceived to be counterproductive to the welfare of nurses in the country. The government limited, if not banned, the migration of nurses and obligated them to serve as reserve forces for the mitigation and control of the illness (CNN, 2020). In exchange, the government mandated the provision of Special Risk Allowances which included an additional PHP500 daily allowance for healthcare workers handling COVID-19 patients (Santos, 2021). However, to their dismay, the implementation of the said program was met with controversies that stemmed

from the reduction to PHP64 after due adjustment in their respective local governments (Lalu, 2021). This has severely aggravated the working conditions of nurses coupled with the persistent shortages of Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) (Sadang, 2021). The difficulties of nurses along with their desire for better pay and benefits especially during the pandemic have led to unmitigated demoralization and loss of commitment that often resulted in resignations or migrations (Sait et al, 2018). In turn, the country's COVID-19 response has been severely affected and impacted in such a way that the healthcare system can longer cope with loss. Hospitals have started degrading their operations not because of inadequate facilities or equipment but due to the lack of nurses (Mendoza, 2021). Numerous factors can be attributed to nursing shortages and nurse turnovers but job satisfaction and morale have been the most frequently cited reasons that require immediate attention (Sait et al, 2018).

The degree to which workers are involved in the work they do for their employer has been shown to have a direct correlation with their level of organizational commitment. Individuals who are visibly engaged in the day-to-day activities of an organization are often portrayed as being aware of and committed to the accomplishment of the institution's goals. Committed employees are often characterized to be highly efficient and productive which often affects their willingness to remain in the organization (Porter et al., 1974). As such, organizational commitment refers to the psychological state that fastens the employee to the organization. Organizational commitment can be classified as affective, continuance, and normative commitment (Allen & Meyer, 1997). Affective commitment is the psychological attachment and involvement of an individual to the organization wherein the work attitudes of the employee towards organizational objectives are compatible with their own (Beck & Wilson, 2000). Continuance commitment is the internal processing of the risks and costs that the individual may incur with leaving the organization usually financially such as salary or professionally such as position. Normative commitment is the feeling of obligation in the performance of one's profession or the desire to reciprocate the benefits received from the organization (McDonald & Makin, 2000). Organizational commitment is associated with job satisfaction which affects productivity and turnover.

There has been a plethora of studies that have examined organizational commitment, but the literature focusing on the factors affecting organizational commitment of nurses during the COVID-19 pandemic is severely limited, making this study stand out. The COVID-19 pandemic brought questions about commitment of nurses towards their jobs. It had been observed that with the presence of the COVID-19 pandemic, a few nurses left their work for fear of the COVID-19 infection. Nurses leaving their profession to as a sign of lack of commitment and venturing into new fields of work. The researcher held administrative roles as a nurse supervisor in the clinical field for two years and eight months in the emergency room while also being a productive bedside member of the medical team. The researcher has been working as a clinical instructor for the past three years, during which time he has interacted with nursing students in all four years of their education, from first year to fourth year. Both fields can benefit by providing factual results from the result of the research study. Speaking these areas of research can lead to a more comprehensive understanding of organizational commitment and its effects for individuals, particularly the staff nurses in their organizations, as well as society. The researcher can delve into these areas to broaden the body of knowledge on commitment and update organizational procedures and strategies.

Research Questions

The main purpose of the study was to correlate the profile and the organizational commitment during the COVID-19 pandemic among staff nurses in a private and government hospital in the year 2022. Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of:
 - 1.1. age;
 - 1.2. sex;
 - 1.3. highest educational attainment;
 - 1.4. number of years in the nursing profession; and
 - 1.5. type of hospital
2. What is the organizational commitment of the staff nurses in terms of:
 - 2.1. continuance commitment;
 - 2.2. affective commitment; and
 - 2.3. normative commitment?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the profile and the continuance commitment of the nursing staff?
4. Is there a significant relationship between the profile and the affective commitment of the nursing staff?
5. Is there a significant relationship between the profile and the normative commitment of the nursing staff?
6. What organizational commitment enhancement plan can be proposed based on the findings of the study?

Literature Review

Organizational Commitment

The term "organizational commitment" is a concept that supposes faced with less attention in Persian management written works or is confused, probably, with the word. Staff commitment is a professional multidimensional construct that is described by the identification of the organization's mission and work ethic (Lober & Skela- Savič, 2014). Many definitions are presented for "commitment", in various views. Several concepts are used as equivalence for "commitment" such as conscience, work ethic,

propensity, and responsibility, although they have conceptual differences, in other words, commitment, such as many organizational psychological concepts has been defined by various methods and measured by different dimensions and scales (Sanagoo et al., 2006). Organizational commitment is defined by management experts as an attitude or a direction that links the individual to an organization (Gautam et al., 2004).

Organizational commitment refers to the extent to which an individual identifies with involvement in a particular organization (Pien Lee et al., 2011). Given definitions of organizational management involve three general issues, including, emotional dependency on an organization, supposed expenditure resulting from leaving the organization, and the sense of commitment to stay in the organization (Lee et al., 2001). A good definition of organizational commitment should primarily be seen in terms of an attitudinal approach. From their perspective, organizational commitment is “the relative strength of an individual’s identification with and involvement in a particular organization that is characterized by three factors: a strong belief in and acceptance of the organization’s goals and values, a willingness to exert considerable effort on behalf of the organization, and strong desire to maintain membership in the organization” (Carman-Tobin, 2011). These three are called emotional, organizational commitment, continual, and assigning or normative, respectively (Meyer et al., 2002).

According to the multidimensional nature of organizational commitment, there is a widespread support from the three-component model of Allen-Meyer. These three parts are more comprehensive and complete, in comparison with organizational commitment dimensions, others defined them, are as follows: (a) normative commitment: the sense of moral and binding obligation to keep being employed. Employees with high normative commitment levels feel should stay in the organization. (b) Emotional commitment: referred to the emotional dependency on the organization, identification with the organization, and involvement in the organization. Due to doing their jobs, the employees by the extreme degree of emotional commitment will continue their jobs in the organization. They work for the company because they like it and want to be part of it. (c) Continued commitment: being aware of relevant expenditures along with leaving the organization. Employees who first connect with the organization, are based on continual commitment; because they require to do their work, therefore, they will stay there. If they abandon the organization, will lose all things (Miandoab et al., 2016; Meyer et al., 1993; Kafashpour et al., 2013; Akbari Haghghi et al., 2014).

In the study by Al-Haroon and Al-Qahtani (2020), a total of 47.88 percent of the nurses agreed with all items connected to the organizational commitment scale, while only 22.3 percent disagreed. There was a significant disparity in the levels of dedication displayed by nurses of varying ages who worked in various settings. The continuous commitment subscale garnered the greatest number of positive responses overall. The majority of nurses demonstrated an average level of commitment to their jobs.

The results of the study by Azizollah et al. (2016) showed the average level of organizational commitment among nurses was 74.24 plus/minus 8.36, emotional commitment was 25.58 plus/minus 3.26. The component and continued commitment were 24.36 plus/minus 4.05 and 24.30 plus/minus 3.48 for normative commitment. According to the findings of this particular study, the level of organizational commitment exhibited by the nurses who took part in the research was only moderate. It is required of the personnel that they accomplish the organization's objectives, perform their responsibilities with love and enthusiasm, and dedicate themselves to the organization. The proper ground conditions need to be created in order to create and preserve these characteristics in the workplace.

According to the findings of the study by Cherian et al., (2018), the majority of nurses were willing to recommend the organization to others. The majority of the nurses with 21-25 years of experience verbalized high job satisfaction levels. On the other hand, the vast majority of nurses who had worked there for between 0 and 5 years expressed a desire to leave the company. More and more nurses wanted to stay when they reached 21 years of experience. Between the ages of 26 and 45, there is a significant increase in the percentage of employees who intend to leave the organization, which then gradually decreases until retirement age. The majority of nurses, regardless of age, preferred moderate levels of organization commitment (90.8 percent for affective commitment, 80.8 percent for continuance commitment, and 92.4 percent for normative commitment). It was shown that nurses' degrees of organizational commitment were significantly related to the degree to which they were satisfied with their jobs. The levels of nurses' affective commitment and total commitment to their jobs were significantly connected to the amount of overall job satisfaction. There was a significant connection between the levels of extrinsic and overall job satisfaction that nurses reported, as well as their levels of organizational commitment overall.

According to the findings of Nagneh et al., (2017), female staff nurses who reported a much stronger organizational commitment also exhibited significantly more caring behavior than other female staff nurses. The outcome was supported by a statistical report that showed the mean score and standard deviation of nurses' caring behavior and organizational commitment to be 74.12 plus or minus 9.61 and 203.1 plus or minus 22.46, respectively. These research findings revealed a statistically significant positive relationship between organizational commitment and caring behavior. As a result, it is critical for managers and nurse leaders to place a greater emphasis on increasing nurses' organizational commitment in order to improve nursing performance.

The level of involvement that nurses had with their jobs was rated as medium, however their dedication to their calling and their organizations was rated as medium to high. According to the findings, each component, including calling, organizational commitment, and work engagement, as well as the overall dimension, had a positive correlation with one another. Organizational commitment plays a partially mediating effect between calling and work engagement (Cao et al., 2019).

Orgambidez and Almeida (2018) studied the effect of job involvement and peer encouragement from supervisors and colleagues on emotional engagement in a nursing staff organization in Portugal. Affective organizational commitment was found to have positive relationships that were statistically significant and favorable in nature with the three engagement dimensions known as vigor, dedication, and absorption. Additionally, support from one's manager as well as support from one's colleagues on the job were found to be positively associated with affective commitment. Significant predictors of supervisor support, vigor, and assimilation were identified in both the linear and hierarchical regression models.

The result of the study by Sattar Khan and Jan (2015) showed that the nurse's perceptions of pay, work, promotion, coworker, supervision, and work environment are the most vital factors of employee satisfaction and important forecasters of organizational commitment. These findings from contemporary scholars provided further support for the hypothesis that job satisfaction and organizational commitment are connected. The statistical evidence supports the premise that there is a connection between being happy in one's job and feeling committed to the organization one works for. According to the findings, the most significant aspects that contribute to the organizational commitment of nurses working at teaching hospitals in Dera Ismail Khan are pay, opportunities for advancement, and the working environment. In addition, there are several characteristics that have a secondary role in determining organizational commitment. Some of these factors include the work itself, fellow workers, and the supervision.

According to the research carried out by Khodadadei et al., (2016), the average score of organizational commitment was 91 with a standard deviation of 10.76 and a level of medium intensity. The clinical competence score averaged out to 74.42 plus or minus 11.69 points, which is considered to be a respectable level. There was no statistically significant connection found between the organizational commitment of the nurses and their clinical ability. The only factor that exhibited a significant link with the quality assurance subarea of clinical competence was the emotional commitment dimension. The clinical competence of nurses was found to have a significant relationship with age, general work experience, monthly wage, job category, location of work, and kind of employment, however their organizational commitment did not have a significant association with the demographic variables that were investigated. According to the findings of this study, nurse managers should make an effort to increase organizational commitment, particularly the emotional commitment of nurses. This would allow for qualified care to be provided to patients while simultaneously boosting trust and durability and promoting nurses' clinical competence.

The results of the study of Mon et al., (2022) revealed that the nurses perceived the three components of organizational commitment at a moderate level. An explanation was given using factors such as years of experience, position, perceived organizational support, and work-life balance. Affective commitment accounts for 38.0% of the overall variation, continuation commitment accounts for 28.3% of the variance, and normative commitment accounts for 35.9% of the variance. The findings of this study can be beneficial to administrators and policymakers in the establishment of policies to promote organizational commitment among nurses based on four predictors. These predictors are generated from the findings of this study, therefore the results of this study are the basis in formulating policies on the organizational commitment. Although differences in an employee's dedication can be explained by organizational characteristics, the differences can be mostly explained by the characteristics of the person as well as the work experiences that they have had. In terms of the differences across occupations, it was shown that individual support from leaders and coworkers had a far stronger influence on organizational commitment in the group of physicians. In contrast, the degree of autonomy in the units and perceived quality of care had a larger impact on the nurses' organizational commitment (Miedaner et al., 2018).

Results show that perceived access to training, training frequency, motivation to learn from training, benefits of training, and supervisory support for training were positively related to the affective and normative components of commitment. Significant differences were found between training and organizational commitment variables between New Zealand and the US.

According to the findings of the study that was carried out by Abd-Elmoniem Amer and Mohammed Atiaa (2019), the organizational commitment level reveals that fifty percent of the critical care nurses had a moderate level of commitment, while only 7.3 percent had a high level of commitment. The study was carried out with the help of a sample size of one hundred and fifty critical care nurses. Despite this, slightly more than half of the employees had a level of work performance that was not sufficient. The findings of the study indicated that there was a strong positive correlation between organizational commitment and work performance among critical care nurses. This conclusion was reached as a result of the investigation. It is proposed that in order to improve nurses' performance and affective commitment, hospitals should give support for their nurses and take decisive action to advance nurses' performance.

Demographic Profile and Organizational Commitment

The respondents' mean score of organizational commitment was 70.45 plus/minus 8.22 and only 72 of the nurses score a high level of organizational commitment. According to the findings of an independent t-test and a one-way analysis of variance, educational level and working ward are substantially related to organizational commitment. According to the findings of a multivariable linear regression, factors such as perceived organizational support, interpersonal relationship quality, job happiness, transformational leadership behavior, educational qualification, and working ward were significant predictors of organizational commitment among nurses. The nurses' degrees of organizational commitment were low. Major determinants of organizational commitment include a person's level of job satisfaction, their perception of organizational support, the presence of transformational leadership behavior, the quality of their interpersonal relationships, and they work in an intensive care unit or operating room (Israel et al., 2017).

Findings in the study of Labrague et al., (2018) revealed that Philippine nurses were moderately committed to and were undecided about whether or not to leave their organization. Significant correlations were found between nurses' organizational commitment and their age, gender, rank, education, and years of work experience. However, significant correlations were found between nurses' turnover intention and their age and education. An inverse relationship was identified between organizational commitment and turnover intention.

In the study of Azizollah et al., (2016), there was no relationship between age and organizational commitment, emotional and continuing commitment, but their relation was significant with normative commitment. According to the findings of Al-Haroon and Al-Qahtani's (2020) research, higher levels of organizational commitment were shown to have a positive correlation with sociodemographic factors including age and nationality. Furthermore, the researchers found that age was the only positive predictor of overall organizational commitment. The means and standard deviations demonstrate that nurses are satisfied with their jobs and that they have a moderate level of commitment to the hospitals where they work. It was revealed that there is a strong positive correlation between job satisfaction and commitment to the organization, with a value of 0.59. In addition, there is a significant correlation between age with both commitment and satisfaction, whereas experience only has a correlation with latter. Moreover, analysis of variance shows that nurses differ in their degree of commitment in terms of their marital status and nationality, whereas they differ in their degree of satisfaction only concerning their nationality (Al-Aameri, 2000).

According to the research carried out by Sepahvand et al., (2017), the vast majority of registered nurses reported a moderate level of organizational commitment, with the continuance commitment receiving the greatest score and the normative commitment receiving the lowest score. A significant correlation was found to exist between the continuance commitment and work experience, as well as staff posts and shifts. Taking into consideration the modest level of organizational commitment exhibited by the subjects in the present study, managers should take the required steps to strengthen the attachment and organizational commitment of nurses and create the groundwork for improving nursing services.

According to the outcomes of Atashzadeh-Shoorideh's (2017) research, the vast majority of registered nurses had a moderate level of organizational commitment, with the continuance commitment receiving the greatest score and the normative commitment receiving the lowest score. A significant correlation was found to exist between the continuance commitment and work experience, as well as staff posts and shifts.

The findings of the research showed that there were no differences in employees' organizational commitment based on either their gender or their marital status. However, there were differences in employees' organizational commitment based on their age, the length of time they had worked for the organization, and their level of education. This article explains that the level of organizational commitment varies according to different subcategories of each demographic trait by delving deeper into the variances that exist between individuals. In addition, the study analyzes the origin of the disparities in organizational commitment related the many subcategories of each demographic attribute, as well as the possible reasons for these discrepancies (Bakoti, 2022).

In another research, the level of organizational commitment was found to be 3.23, the level of continuation commitment was found to be 3.29, the level of normative commitment was found to be 3.28, and the level of emotional commitment was found to be 3.12. According to the findings of the study, there is a meaningful distinction between organizational commitment and institutional framework. In addition, it was found in the research that the level of affective commitment varies significantly based on factors such as professional experience, institutional structure, and age. As a direct consequence of this, it was discovered that the levels of organizational commitment exhibited by family physicians were significantly higher than those exhibited by physicians who worked in public hospitals. In addition, the study found that when both the age of the physicians and the length of their professional careers increased, the affective commitment levels of the physicians dropped. (Yağar & Dökme, 2019).

Profile of Nurses

In the study of Feliciano et al. (2019), most of the nurses' demographic profile showed: a mean age of 31.64 years old, 69.20 percent were single, 62.10 percent were female, 76.80 percent were under staff nurse position, 60.70 percent were under 1 to 30 years of service that had a monthly salary of Php 6,000-60,000.

According to the findings of the research, participants' levels of organizational commitment were found to be 3.23, levels of continuation commitment were found to be 3.29, normative commitment levels were found to be 3.28, and affective commitment levels were found to be 3.23. Women have consistently held a majority of positions in nursing since the profession's inception. Men are less likely to get into this line of work than women. The employment of preconceived notions is the primary contributor to this problem. The nursing workforce is gender imbalanced, which has led to fewer males entering the field. Additionally, this imbalance has resulted in a stigma attached to male nurses. Due to the multicultural limits that exist, the word "compassion" is always mirrored in a female caregiver. Men, on the other hand, are regarded to be less sympathetic and more macho, and as a result, they are stereotypically incapable of nursing and unfit for the profession. 3.12 as their level of active commitment. The research shows that there is a large gap between organizational commitment and institutional structure. Affective commitment level also varies significantly according to professional experience, institutional structure, and age, as the study found. This finding was another interesting finding from the research. As a consequence of this, it was discovered that the organizational commitment levels of family physicians were higher than

the organizational commitment levels of physicians who worked in public hospitals. According to the findings of the study, levels of affective commitment fell as both the age of the physicians and the amount of professional experience they had rose.

According to the data provided by the United States Census Bureau, there are 3.2 million female nurses, which accounts for 91 percent of the total, while there are only 330,000 male nurses, which accounts for 9 percent (Vadivala, 2022). According to Mao et al. (2021), in spite of the fact that the gender gap has shrunk in other professions like medicine, law, and business, nursing continues to be a field that is predominately held by women.

In accordance with the provisions of Article IV, Section 12 of Republic Act No. 9173 of 2002, all individuals who wish to be granted a license to engage in the profession of nursing are required to pass an exam that is written. This examination is to be administered by the Board at such times and locations as may be authorized by the Commission: With the proviso that it must comply with Republic Act No. 8981, also referred to as the "PRC Modernization Act of 2000." In addition, the prerequisites for taking the licensing exam are outlined in Section 13, which can be found here. An applicant must, at the time of filing his or her application, establish to the satisfaction of the Board that in order to be admitted to the examination for nurses, he or she meets the following requirements: (a) He or she is a citizen of the Philippines, or a citizen or subject of a country that permits Filipino nurses to practice within its territorial limits on the same basis as the subject or citizen of such a country: He or she has a bachelor's degree in nursing from an accredited school in the Philippines Provided, however, that the requirements for the registration or licensing of nurses in said country are substantially the same as those prescribed in this Act; (b) He or she is of good moral character; and (c) He or she is the holder of a Bachelor's Degree in Nursing from an institution of higher education that complies with the standards of nursing education duly recognized by the appropriate government agency. The completion of a bachelor's degree program in nursing, which typically takes four years, is required as a bare minimum for admittance into the field of professional nursing. (Rogado, n.d.).

According to the findings of the research conducted by Pires et al. (2018), the majority of patients are coming from private hospitals (76.10 percent), while just 23.9 percent are coming from public hospitals. In addition, 46.8 percent of the nurses had between 1 and 5 years of experience, making them the most experienced group. The next most experienced group had 6 or more years of experience, making up 31.980 percent of the population. The final 21.30 percent of nurses had between 3 months and one year of experience, making them the least experienced group.

Methodology

Research Design

This study utilized quantitative descriptive-correlational research design since it sought to determine the relationship and association of one variable to the other and understand the variable of the study without any intervention.

It is a quantitative research as it determined the frequency of a given condition while quantifying the relationships between variables using a questionnaire.

It is a descriptive research as it sought to understand the relationship of variables without any intervention. This study sought to determine the relationship between the profile and the organizational commitment of the nursing staff. It is used in determining the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, highest educational attainment, and number of years in the nursing profession. The descriptive design is also used in determining the organizational commitment of the staff nurses in terms of continuance commitment, affective commitment, and normative commitment.

It is a correlational research as it determined the correlation of the variables and how they affected each other. Specifically, it determined the strength of the relationship between the profile and the organizational commitment of the nursing staff. The correlational design is used in assessing whether there is a significant relationship between the profile and the organizational commitment of the nursing staff.

It is a descriptive correlational research as it provided data for describing the status of phenomena or the relationships between phenomena in terms of the frequency and characteristics of a condition in a population at a specific point in time (Ihudiebube-Splendor & Chikeme, 2020).

Respondents

Respondents in this study included staff nurses working in six (6) different public and private hospitals located within the municipality of Midsayap. The following is an approximate breakdown of the population of respondents : Dr. Amado B. Diaz Provincial Foundation Hospital- twenty four (24), a level I and a 50-bed capacity government hospital, Community Health Service Cooperative Hospital - sixty two (62), a level I and 52-bed capacity private hospital, Midsayap Doctors Specialist Hospital Incorporated - twenty four (24), a level I and 38-bed capacity private hospital, Anecito P. Pesante, SR Memorial Hospital Incorporated - eighteen (18), a level I and 98-bed capacity hospital. In accordance with the provisions of Administrative Order (AO) No. 2020-016 issued by the Department of Health of the Philippines, the aforementioned hospitals are required to allot a minimum of 20% of their total bed capacity to private hospitals and a minimum of 30% of their total bed capacity to government hospitals during the pandemic in order facilitate the admission of patients who are infected with COVID-19. A total of one hundred twenty eight (128) staff nurses will be recruited.

Instruments

A two-part questionnaire was utilized in the study. Part one pertained to determining the demographic profile in terms of age, sex, highest educational attainment, number of years in the nursing profession, and type of hospital.

Part two of the questionnaire was a standard tool for organizational commitment. The scale was developed by Meyer et al. (1993). The questionnaire had a total of eighteen questions, six for each of three dimensions: affective commitment (six items), continuance commitment (six items), and normative commitment (six items). The data was collected using a scale of the Likert type with five points, where one (1) indicated "strongly disagree" and five (5) indicated "strongly agree." higher score showed a greater level of professional commitment. Parametric scores and interpretation are as follows: 1.00 – 1.80 is very low, 1.81 – 2.60 is low, 2.61 – 3.40 is neither low nor high, 3.41 – 4.20 is high, and 4.21 – 5.00 is very high.

The EFA demonstrates that it can be divided into three dimensions, which contributes to both its reliability and validity. According to the findings of the CFA, the RNI values fall somewhere in the range of 0.836 to 0.979, and the PNFI values fall somewhere in the range of 0.738 to 0.845 on the original scale. In this investigation, the findings of CFA revealed that the model had the following: $\chi^2 = 2896$, $df = 5$, $p = 0.000$, $GFI = 0.957$, $RMSEA = 0.133$, $CFI = 0.978$.

Procedure

Preliminary. The first step that was done was to present three prospective titles for studies for approval. After the title was finalized and accepted, an adviser was selected. In order for the study to move forward, it was necessary to have approval from the Dean of the College of Allied Health Sciences, the Chief Academic Officer, and respective chief of the hospital. After first step approval had been given, the study was next presented to an expert panel during the design hearing for approval. To proceed with the report, the paper was approved by the University of the Visayas-Research Ethics Committee (UV-REC). Before beginning the selection of respondents, the researcher waited for the notice to proceed. Due to the data will be collected in person, the researcher followed the guidelines established by the Inter-agency Task Force (IATF) during the face-to-face encounter. This was done to guarantee that the respondents and the researcher remained safe during the entire process. The inclusion and exclusion criteria were used as a guide during the process of selecting respondents to participate in the study when data were being collected.

Actual Data Gathering. Questionnaires were be distributed to qualified respondents and collected the same day. When the questionnaires were returned, they were double-checked for missing or unanswered items. If this occurred the form were returned to the respondent for completion. All completed questionnaires were collected and compiled.

Post Data Gathering. Responses were tallied and subjected to descriptive and inferential statistics treatments. The completed questionnaires were shredded at the end of the study. A soft copy of the tabulated responses was kept for reference purposes only and was deleted once the study was completed.

Ethical Considerations

The following principles were strictly observed in the conduct of the study.

Protection of Human Rights. To protect the respondents' interests, three ethical standards were followed. These are the ideals of human dignity, beneficence, and justice.

The first principle is respect for individuals. The participants in the study had the right to decide whether or not they wanted to take part in the study, which were not subject to any form of pressure, limitation, or undue influence. It was made clear to the researchers that the respondents were willing to take part in the study by means of a consent form. The respondents were made to understand their role in the study especially in answering the survey questionnaire about the factors influencing professional commitment among staff nurses during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The second principle is beneficence which is related to the researcher's responsibility to ensure that the study's benefits were maximized while the risks were minimized. The principle required the researcher to ensure not to harm the respondents which were accomplished in the research by not implementing any treatments, procedures, or alternatives.

The third principle is justice which explains how respondents were chosen in an objective manner. When recruiting individuals, the researcher used the inclusion and exclusion criteria that were established. In the course of the research, there were no subjects who were vulnerable. Without any form of bias or prejudice on the part of the researcher, everyone of the respondents went through the same process of data collecting and data analysis.

Transparency. The researcher aims to present the study in either local, national, or international research congress through oral or poster presentation.

Risk-Benefit Ratio Determination. The following significant potential benefits for the respondents were assured to mitigate the hazards and maximize the benefits of the study.

Benefits. This principle, we were able to derive the following benefits: (a) Staff Nurses would be able to feel less load as a result of

organizational intervention programs that will address the numerous problems and difficulties they faced during the COVID-19 pandemic. As a result, a positive working environment that was essential for the promotion of their well-being was made available to them at their place of employment. They were informed of the organizational intervention plan that they utilized during this time of pandemic in order to favorably impact job retention; (b) Nurse Managers will be able to recognize the difficulties that are encountered by the staff nurses in their particular units. As a consequence of this, they will be able to provide adequate support on how to address their problems and appreciate the efforts that follow the intervention plan that they will be implementing; (c) Hospital Administrators will be able to make available essential resources that would allow the staff nurses to work efficiently and effectively. (d) Policymakers will be prompted to evaluate current laws and regulations that support various healthcare institutions, which is a vital role that hospital administrators play in ensuring that all difficulties and obstacles that are faced by staff nurses are resolved. e) The researcher will be able to gain knowledge relating to the variables being studied and gain insights into the conduct of nursing research, which will be a great contribution to the medical profession especially in the nursing administration; and (f) Future Researchers will benefit by gaining access to new information. There may be a need to bring revisions or amendments to existing laws in order to better implement them in order to address prevailing issues caused by the pandemic. It will provide essential understanding about the several effective leadership styles that can be utilized whenever there is a crisis involving the health system. The outcomes of the study could be confirmed or refuted by conducting the same research again. In addition, the findings have the potential to become a researchable issue in future research.

Risks. The following risks were avoided if not minimized: (a) physical harm – the researcher only used the survey questionnaire; (b) physical inconvenience, fatigue, or weariness – respondents were only asked for 5-10 minutes of their free time (during their break time or after work) to complete the questionnaire; (c) mental or psychological discomfort – the questionnaire were not asked prying and sensitive personal questions; (d) social damage – respondents were not subjected to stigma, as anonymity was strictly observed and there will be no questions regarding sensitive issues, (e) loss of privacy – confidentiality and security of privacy were observed at all times, (f) loss of time – a questionnaire were answered during their free time; and (g) monetary expenses – the respondents did not incur any expenses in joining the study as no fees were collected. Data gathering were done in the workplace of the respondents.

Informed Consent. In order for this study to proceed, participants had to give their informed consent. The participants in the study were provided with an informed consent form to signify their voluntarily participation. The following components were included in the informed consent form:

Status of the respondents. The respondents were made aware that this study was carried out as a way of the researcher satisfying the academic requirements for the Master's degree.

Study Goals. The study aimed to determine the profile of the organizational commitment of nurses during the covid-19 pandemic in private and government hospitals in Midsayap, Cotabato in 2022.

Procedures. The researcher began by submitting a request for authorization to the Dean of the College of Graduate School in order to be able to conduct the study. It was followed by a design hearing with a panel of experts who assessed the technical soundness. After the incorporation of the recommendations, the research was presented to the institutional review board for ethics so that it could be evaluated for its ethical validity. After notice was given to proceed, the researcher started the selection process for the respondents. Each and every questionnaire was compiled after being gathered, analyzed, and organized into tables

Potential Risks. The risk to which respondents were exposed is similar to the risk they encountered in their everyday lives. The study only required replying to a survey questionnaire. Furthermore, the questionnaire did not contain any sensitive questions which may harm the respondents psychologically or emotionally. Discussions on the potential risk and how they were reduced were addressed in the preceding paragraphs on risk-benefit assessment.

Alternatives. The use of a survey questionnaire was the primary method that was employed throughout the data collection process. The respondents were not subjected to any interventions or treatments, and as a result, the alternatives were not applied.

Compensation. Only words of gratitude were used to thank the respondents. The respondents were not given any compensation or incentives considering that the review will only involve answering a questionnaire. This was also adapted so as not to influence participation as it may be misinterpreted as inducements.

Pledge of Confidentiality. Provisions of the Data Privacy Act of 2012 were strictly observed in the conduct of the study. Also, specific confidentiality measures were instituted to preserve the anonymity of the respondents. A specific section on privacy and confidentiality was provided for the discussion below.

Voluntary Consent. The researcher insured that the respondent's consent was voluntarily given for them to be considered valid study participants.

The Right to Withdraw and Withhold Information. In the event that a respondent chose to withdraw from the study or refused to have any information published, they were not subject to any kind of sanction or penalty.

Contact Information. The researcher provided his contact number and the name of the University to the respondents. Any questions or

clarifications were answered without hesitation, especially in the occurrence of doubts or complaints about the conduct of the research. Respondents were able to contact the Research Ethics Committee at 416-8067 or email at rec@uv.edu.ph.

Authorization to Access Private Information. No private information of respondents was accessed by the researcher.

Privacy and Confidentiality Procedures. Respondents were given privacy by allowing them to answer the questionnaire in a location conducive to complete concentration and without interruption. In order to maintain respondents' privacy, the researcher did not acquire personal information such as names and addresses. The study maintained strict confidentiality. Each questionnaire was completed and labeled using only numbers. The completed questionnaires were stored in a cabinet that only the researcher could access. While the compiled data were stored on the computer, both the computer and its files were password-protected. The compiled data were presented in tabular format.

Compensation and Incentives. The researcher expressed appreciation to the respondents for their participation in the research and thanked them for their time. The participation in the study was entirely voluntary, it was also indicated that the respondents did not receive any payment or other form of inducement for their participation.

Recruitment. After receiving notification to proceed from the UV-IRB, the process of recruitment began. Inclusion and exclusion served as the primary criteria for this study. The recruitment was done through the use of a face-to-face intercept.

Debriefing, Communication, and Referrals. To connect with the respondents, friendliness and politeness were the two most important qualities to exhibit. In the event that concerns relating to the study arose, both the investigator and the enumerators were readily available.

Conflict of Interest. The researcher declared no conflict of interest.

Collaborative Terms of Reference. This activity was not carried out in collaboration with any individual or institution; rather, participation in it was necessary for educational purposes. The researcher held intellectual property rights. However, the adviser to the researcher was permitted to co-author this work. The terms of reference consequently did not apply.

Vulnerability Assessment. As a guideline, there were no vulnerable individuals served as research participants. The researcher ensured that none of the respondents belonged to vulnerable groups by taking the necessary precautions.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the tables as answers to the research problems on the profile on the organizational commitment of nurses during covid-19 pandemic gathered from the survey conducted in the hospitals in the Municipality of Midsayap, Province of Cotabato. These provide the data on the continuance, affective, and normative commitments to their organizations and their correlation to the profile of nurses.

Profile of the Staff Nurses

Table 1 is the presentation of the data on the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, highest educational attainment, number of years in the nursing profession, and type of hospital. The results are presented in terms of the frequency (*f*) and percentage (%),

Table 1. *Profile of the Staff Nurses*

<i>Profile</i>	<i>f</i>	<i>%</i>
Age		
19 to 35 years old (Young adulthood)	86	67.19
36 to 55 years old (Middle adulthood)	42	32.81
Sex		
Male	26	20.30
Female	102	79.70
Educational Attainment		
College Degree Holder	115	89.80
With Master's Degree Units	4	3.10
With Master's Degree	8	6.20
With Doctoral Degree	1	.80
Years of Service		
Less than 3 years	14	10.94
3 to 6 years	46	35.94
7 to 10 years	33	25.78
Above 10 years	35	27.34
Type of Hospital		
Government	24	18.80
Private	104	81.20

Note: *n*=128.

Table 2. Organizational Commitment of the Staff Nurses

Items	Mean score	SD	Interpretation
Factor 1: Continuance professional commitment			
1. I have put too much into the actuarial profession to consider changing now	3.41	1.083	Agree
2. Changing professions now would be difficult for me to do	3.73	1.090	Agree
3. Too much of my life would be disrupted if I were to change my profession	3.42	1.024	Agree
4. It would be costly for me to change my profession now	3.81	1.033	Agree
5. (R) There are no pressures to keep me from changing professions*	3.54	.971	Agree
6. Changing professions now would require considerable personal sacrifice	2.07	.949	Disagree
Factor mean	3.33	.480	Neither low nor high
Factor 2: Affective professional commitment			
1. Being an actuary is important to my self image	3.91	.948	Agree
2. (R) I regret having entered the actuarial profession*	3.93	1.102	Agree
3. I am proud to be in the actuarial profession	4.45	.886	Strongly agree
4. (R) I dislike being an actuary*	4.10	.979	Agree
5. (R) I do not identify with the actuarial profession*	3.73	1.031	Agree
6. I am enthusiastic about being an actuary	4.02	.922	Agree
Factor mean	4.02	.672	High
Factor 3: Normative professional commitment			
1. I believe people who have been trained in a profession have a responsibility to stay in that profession for a reasonable period of time	3.82	.951	Agree
2. (R) I do not feel any obligation to remain in the actuarial profession*	3.49	1.115	Agree
3. I feel a responsibility to the actuarial profession to continue in it	3.97	.822	Agree
4. Even if it were to my advantage, I do not feel that it would be right to leave the actuarial profession now	3.70	.864	Agree
5. I would feel guilty if I left the actuarial profession	3.51	.956	Agree
6. I am an actuary because of a sense of loyalty to the profession	4.16	.801	Agree
Factor mean	3.76	.567	High
Grand mean	3.71	.441	High

Note: n=128. A score of 1.00 – 1.80 is very low (Strongly disagree), 1.81 – 2.60 is low (Disagree), 2.61 – 3.40 is neither low nor high (Neither agree nor disagree), 3.41 – 4.20 is high (Agree), and 4.21 – 5.00 is very high (Strongly Agree)

Table 3. Relationship between Profile and Continuance Commitment

Independent Variables	Chi-square	p value	Cramer's V value	Decision	Interpretation
Age	4.180E2	.158	--	Failed to reject the Ho	Not significant
Sex	12.480	.642	--	Failed to reject the Ho	Not significant
Educational Attainment	28.581	.973	--	Failed to reject the Ho	Not significant
Years of service	3.465E2	.107	--	Failed to reject the Ho	Not significant
Type of hospital	12.492	.641	--	Failed to reject the Ho	Not significant

Legend: Significant if p value is < .05. Dependent variable: Continuance Commitment. Cramer's V interpretation: A value of 0.1 - 0.3 is weak association, 0.4 - 0.5 is medium association, and >0.5 is strong association.

Table 4. Relationship between Profile and Affective Commitment

Independent Variables	Chi value	p value	Cramer's V value	Decision	Interpretation
Age	3.901E2	.814	--	Failed to reject the Ho	Not significant
Sex	24.260	.084	--	Failed to reject the Ho	Not significant
Educational Attainment	34.979	.920	--	Failed to reject the Ho	Not significant
Years of service	2.923E2	.959	--	Failed to reject the Ho	Not significant
Type of hospital	21.818	.149	--	Failed to reject the Ho	Not significant

Legend: Significant if p value is < .05. Dependent variable: Affective Commitment. Cramer's V interpretation: A value of 0.1 - 0.3 is weak association, 0.4 - 0.5 is medium association, and >0.5 is strong association.

Table 5. Relationship between Profile and Normative Commitment

Independent Variables	Chi value	p value	Cramer's V value	Decision	Interpretation
Age	4.317E2	.071	--	Failed to reject the Ho	Not significant
Sex	15.234	.435	--	Failed to reject the Ho	Not significant
Educational Attainment	32.642	.915	--	Failed to reject the Ho	Not significant
Years of service	3.966E2	.001	.454	Reject Ho	Significant
Type of hospital	19.042	.212	--	Failed to reject the Ho	Not significant

Legend: Significant if p value is < .05. Dependent variable: Affective Commitment. Cramer's V interpretation: A value of 0.1 - 0.3 is weak association, 0.4 - 0.5 is medium association, and >0.5 is strong association.

Table 6. Relationship between Profile and Organizational Commitment

Independent Variables	Chi value	p value	Cramer's V value	Decision	Interpretation
Age	8.144E2	.662	--	Failed to reject the Ho	Not significant
Sex	25.556	.783	--	Failed to reject the Ho	Not significant
Educational Attainment	1.050E2	.249	--	Failed to reject the Ho	Not significant
Years of service	7.489E2	.021	.528	Reject Ho	Significant
Type of hospital	52.030	.014	.638	Reject Ho	Significant

The majority of the respondents were young adults or belonging to 19 to 35 years old and the majority of them were females and college degree holders. Furthermore, most of the respondents had served their organization for 3 to 6 years already and the majority of the respondents are connected with a private hospital.

In terms of continuance commitment, this was rated as neither low nor high while affective commitment and normative commitment were rated as high. Overall, the organizational commitment of the respondents was high.

Age, sex, educational attainment, years of service, and type of hospital did not have a significant relationship with continuance commitment. Age, sex, educational attainment, years of service, and type of hospital did not have a significant relationship with affective commitment. There was a significant relationship between years of experience and normative commitment while age, sex, educational attainment, and type of hospital did not have a significant relationship with normative commitment.

Significant relationships were seen between years of experience and overall organizational commitment as well as type of hospital and overall organizational commitment. While age, sex, and educational attainment did not have a significant relationship with overall organizational commitment.

Conclusions

In conclusion, years of experience and the type of hospital influence organizational commitment. The longer the years of experience, the higher the organizational commitment. Also, as the type of hospital becomes a private hospital, this increases the organizational commitment. The findings of the study affirm the Multidimensional Model of Organizational Commitment of Allen and Meyer (1997), the model proposes that the high level of organizational commitment experienced by the nurses encompasses the three simultaneous mindsets encompassing affective, normative, and continuance organizational commitment. As an output of the study, an organizational commitment enhancement plan was created.

References

- Abd-Elmoniem Amer, H., & Mohammed Atiea, K. (2019). Organizational commitment and job performance among critical care nurses at Zagazig University Hospitals, Egypt. *International Journal of Novel Research in Healthcare and Nursing*, 6(1), 312-325.
- Akbari Haghghi, F., Koohi Rostamkalae, Z., Pourreza, A., & Rahimi Forshani, A. (2014). Surveying the employed nurses' organizational commitment in selected Tehran University of Medical Sciences Hospitals. *Journal of Hospital*, 13(2), 63-73
- Al-Aameri, A. S. (2000). Job satisfaction and organizational commitment for nurses. *Saudi Medical Journal*, 21(6), 531-535.
- Al-Haroon, H. I., & Al-Qahtani, M. F. (2020). Assessment of organizational commitment among nurses in a major public hospital in Saudi Arabia. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Healthcare*, 13, 519-526. <https://doi.org/10.2147/JMDH.S256856>
- Alibudbud, R. (2022, May 23). When the "heroes" "don't feel cared for": The migration and resignation of Philippine nurses amidst the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of Global Health*. <https://jogh.org/2022/jogh-12-03011>.
- Atashzadeh-Shoorideh, F. (2017). The relationship between some demographic characteristics and organizational commitment of nurses working in the Social Security Hospital of Khorramabad. *Electronic Physician*, 9(6).
- Azizollah, A., Sarani, H., Mohammadi, S., & Robabi, H. (2016). Organizational commitment in nurses. *International Journal of Advanced Biotechnology and Research*, 7(5), 1841-1846.
- Bakotić, D. (2022). How do demographic characteristics relate to organizational commitment? Evidence from Croatia. *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja*, 35(1), 3551-3570. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2021.1997624>
- Bartlett, K., & Kang, D.S. (2004). Training and organizational commitment among nurses in New Zealand and United States public hospitals experiencing industry and organizational change. *Nursing Research*, 53(2), 96-101. <https://doi.org/10.1080/1367886042000299799>
- Beck, K., & Wilson, C. (2000). Development of affective organizational commitment: A cross-sequential examination of change with tenure. *Journal of Vocational Behavior*, 56(1), 114-136. <https://doi.org/10.1006/jvbe.1999.1712>
- Buchan J & Catton H. (2021, October 21). COVID-19 and the International Supply of Nurses. From https://www.icn.ch/system/files/documents/2020-07/COVID19_internationalsupplyofnurses_Report_FINAL.pdf.

- Cao, Y., Liu, J., Liu, K., Yang, M., & Liu, Y. (2019). The mediating role of organizational commitment between calling and work engagement of nurses: A cross-sectional study. *International Journal of Nursing Sciences*, 6(3), 309-314. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnss.2019.05.004>.
- Carman-Tobin, M. B. (2011). *Organizational commitment among licensed practical nurses: exploring associations with empowerment, conflict and trust*. (Published Dissertation), University of Iowa, 2011. <http://ir.uiowa.edu/etd/2678>.
- Cherian, S., Alkhatib, J., & Aggarwal, M. (2018). Relationship between organizational commitment and job satisfaction of nurses in Dubai hospital. *Journal of Advances in Social Science and Humanities*, 4, 36373-36400. <https://doi.org/10.15520/jassh41276>.
- Department of Health (DOH). (2021). Status of the Philippine human resources for health. <http://https://hhrdb.doh.gov.ph/nhrhmp/>
- Gautam, T., Van Dick, R., & Wagner, U. (2004). Organizational identification and organizational commitment: Distinct aspects of two related concepts. *Asian Journal of Social Psychology*, 7(3), 301–315.
- Israel, B., Kifle, W., Tigist, D., & Fantahun, W. (2017). Organizational commitment and its predictors among nurses working in Jimma University Specialized Teaching Hospital, Southwest Ethiopia. *Primary Health Care: Open Access*, 7(1).
- Jackson, A. (2021, September 18). 'Burnt out': Nurses battle COVID-19, resignations in Philippines. *PhilStar Global*. <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2021/09/18/2128038/burnt-out-nurses-battle-covid-resignations-philippines>
- Kafashpour, A., Mortazavi, S., & Pour, S. (2013). Impact of psychological contracts on organizational trust and commitment of nurses in Ghaem hospital-Mashhad province. *Journal of Hospital*, 11(4), 65–74.
- Khodadadei, N., Rezaei, B., & Salehi, S. (2016). Investigating the relationship of organizational commitment and clinical competence (Case study: Nurses working in Montazeri Hospital, City of Najafabad, Iran 2015). *International Journal of Medical Research & Health Sciences*, 5(S), 308-316.
- Labrague, L. J., McEnroe – Petite, D. M., Tsaras, K., Cruz, J. P., Colet, P. C., & Gloe, D. S. (2018). Organizational commitment and turnover intention among rural nurses in the Philippines: Implications for nursing management. *International Journal of Nursing Sciences*, 5(4), 403-408. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijnss.2018.09.001>.
- Lalu JG. (2021, August, 14). Nurse who died of COVID-19 gets P7,000 hazard pay, not P30,000 – daughter. <https://newsinfo.inquirer.net/1321435/nurse-who-died-of-covid-19-gets-p7000-hazard-pay-not-p30000-daughter#ixzz7D1tWWH7n>.
- Lee, K., Allen, N. J., Meyer, J. P., & Rhee, K. (2001). The three-component model of organizational commitment: An application to South Korea. *Applied Psychology*, 50(4), 596–614.
- Locsin pushes IATF to lift deployment ban on nurses or 'pay big money' (2020, August, 28). *Locsin pushes IATF to lift deployment ban on nurses or 'pay big money'*. *CNN Philippines*. <https://www.cnnphilippines.com/news/2020/8/28/Healthcare-workers-nurse-deployment-ban-Locsin.html>. Accessed: 21 October 2021.
- Lorber, M., & Skela-Savič, B. (2014). Factors affecting nurses' organizational commitment. *Obzornik zdravstvene nege*, 48(4), 294–301.
- Mcdonald, D. J. , & Makin, P. J. (2000). The psychological contract, organisational commitment and job satisfaction of temporary staff. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 21(2), 84–91.
- Mendoza B. (2021, October 21). Nurses leaving in droves – PHA. *The Manila Times*. <https://www.manilatimes.net/2021/10/20/news/national/nurses-leaving-in-droves-pha/1819057>.
- Meyer, J. P., & Allen, N. J. (1997). *Commitment in the workplace. Theory, research and application*. Thousand Oaks: Sage.
- Meyer, J.P., Allen, N. J., & Smith, C. A. (1993). Commitment to organizations and occupations: Extension and test of a three-component conceptualization. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 78, 538–551. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0021-9010.78.4.538>.
- Meyer, J. P., Stanley, D. J., Herscovitch, L., & Topolnytsky, L. (2002). Affective, continuance and normative commitment to the organization: A meta-analysis of antecedents, correlates, and consequences. *Journal of Vocational Behaviour*, 61, 20-52.
- Meyer, J. P., Allen, N. J., & Smith, C. A. (1993). Commitment to organizations and occupations: Extension and test of a three-component conceptualization. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 78(4), 538.
- Miandoab, N. Y., Zare S., Salar, A. R., & Shahrakipour, M. (2016). The survey of the organizational commitment among Zahedan medical sciences staff in 2015. *Indian Journal of Public Health Research and Development*, 7(3), 293–297. <https://doi.org/10.5958/0976-5506.2016.00174.1>.
- Miedaner, F., Kuntz, L., Enke, C., Roth, B., & Nitzsche, A. (2018). Exploring the differential impact of individual and organizational

factors on organizational commitment of physicians and nurses. *BMC Health Service Research*, 18(180). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12913-018-2977-1>.

Mon, E. E., Akkadechanunt, T., & Chitpakdee, B. (2022). Factors predicting organizational commitment of nurses in general hospitals: A descriptive-predictive study. *Nursing and Health Sciences*, 24(3), 610-617. <https://doi.org/10.1111/nhs.12953>

Naghneh, M. H. K., Tafreshi, M. Z., Naderi, M., Shakeri, N., Bolourchifard, F., & Goyaghaj, N. S. (2017). The relationship between organizational commitment and nursing care behavior. *Electron Physician*, 29(7), 4835-4840. <https://doi.org/10.19082/4835>.

Noraazian & Khalip (2016). A three-component conceptualization of organizational commitment. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 6(12).

Orgambidez, A., & Almeida, H. (2018). Predictors of organizational commitment in nursing: Results from Portugal. *Investigacion y Educacion en Enfermeria*, 36(1), e14. <https://doi.org/10.17533/udea.iee.v36n1e14>.

Pien Lee, S., Chitpakdee, B., & Chontawan, R.b. (2011). Factors predicting organizational commitment among nurses in state hospitals, Malaysia. *IMJM*, 10(2), 21-28.

Porter, L. W. , Steers, R. M. , Mowday, R. T. , & Boulian, P. V. (1974). Organizational commitment, job satisfaction, and turnover among psychiatric technicians. *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 59(5), 603-609. [10.1037/h0037335](https://doi.org/10.1037/h0037335)

Private Hospital Association of the Philippines (PHAP). (2021). Philippine Staff Shortages During the Pandemic. From <https://www.reuters.com/world/asia-pacific/overwhelmed-philippines-hospitals-hit-by-staff-resignations-2021-08-16/>

Sanagoo, A., Nikraves, M., & Dabbaghi, F. (2006). Organizational commitment from Nursing & Midwifery faculty members' perspective. *Razi Journal of Medical Sciences*, 13(52), 83-92.

Santos AP. (2021). Philippines: Nurses threaten mass resignation amid COVID surge. <https://p.dw.com/p/3zg0w>.

Sattar Khan, A., & Jan, F. (2015). The study of organization commitment and job satisfaction among hospital nurses. A survey of District Hospitals of Dera Ismail Khan. *Global Journal of Management and Business Research: A Administration and Management*, 15(1).

Sepahvand, F., Atashzadeh-Shoorideh, F., Parvizy, S., & Tafreshi, M. Z. (2017). The relationship between some demographic characteristics and organizational commitment of nurses working in the Social Security Hospital of Khorramabad. *Electron Physician*, 9(6), 4503-4509. <https://doi.org/10.19082/4503>.

Valmonte, K. (2022, June 21). No shortage of nurses but low pay, lack of tenure driving them abroad. *PhilStar Global*. <https://www.philstar.com/headlines/2022/06/21/2189974/no-shortage-nurses-low-pay-lack-tenure-driving-them-abroad>

Yağar, F., & Dökme, S. (2019). The relationship between organizational commitment and demographic variables of physicians in public institutions. *International Journal of Healthcare Management*, 12(1), 81-86. <https://doi.org/10.1080/20479700.2017.1406678>.

Feliciano, E., Feliciano, A., Feliciano-Pena, L. V., Mejia, P. C., & Osman, A. (2019). Competency of nurses in the context of Philippine healthcare. *International Journal of Caring Sciences*, 12(3), 1402.

Mao, A., Cheong, P. L., Van, I. K., & Tam, H. L. (2021). "I am called girl, but that doesn't matter" -perspectives of male nurses regarding gender-related advantages and disadvantages in professional development. *BMC Nursing*, 20(1), 24. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12912-021-00539-w>.

Republic Act No. 9173 (2002). An act providing for a more responsive nursing profession, repealing for the purpose Republic Act No. 7164, otherwise known as "The Philippine Nursing Act of 1991" and for other purposes.

Vadivala, R. (2022). Nursing: A female dominated profession – gender stereotyping. *Journal of Pioneering Medical Sciences Blogs*. <https://blogs.jpmsonline.com/2022/03/26/nursing-a-female-dominated-profession-gender>

Pires, B. S. M., Oliveira, L. Z. F., Siqueira, C. L., Feldman, L. B., Oliveira, R. A., & Gasparino, R. C. (2018). Nurse work environment: Comparison between private and public hospitals. *Einstein (Sao Paulo)*, 16(4), eAO4322. https://doi.org/10.31744/einstein_journal/2018AO4322.

Rogado, M. I. C. (n.d.). Nursing in the Philippines. *Nihon Shuchu Chiryō Igakukai Zasshi*. From https://www.academia.edu/75762510/Nursing_in_the_Philippines

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Michael John A. Castillo, MANM, RN
Notre Dame Of Midsayap College – Philippines